

Review Article

The impacts of extreme weather events on health services and systems: A systematic review of reviews

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Beyond health impacts, Extreme Weather Events (EWEs) disrupt health services and systems, an aspect often overlooked in favour of individual health outcomes. This systematic review of reviews aimed to systematically map the diverse impacts of EWEs on health services and systems, offering essential information to enhance disaster preparedness across different healthcare delivery settings.

Study design: A systematic review of reviews was chosen as the best method to achieve the study objective, following PRISMA guidelines for conduct and reporting.

Methods: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science were searched for narrative or systematic reviews, with or without a meta-analysis, published in the past 10 years. We evaluated the impact of floods, storms, heatwaves, cold spells, and wildfires on different components, from pre-hospital care to primary care and pharmacies. Results were thematically analysed to categorise impacts by hazard type, affected component, and impact type.

Results: A total of 114 reviews were included, detailing EWEs' consequences on health services and systems, and showcasing the heterogeneity of impacts across different healthcare delivery settings and hazard types. Floods and storms disrupt hospital and pre-hospital services through infrastructure damage and road closures. Heatwaves increase ambulance dispatches, emergency department visits, hospitalisations, and primary care use, due to heat exposure and chronic disease exacerbation. Increased particulate matter levels during wildfires was also associated with increased healthcare use.

Conclusions: These findings highlight the significant impact of EWEs on health services and systems, and underscore the need for appropriate adaptation measures. They offer practical evidence to enhance health system preparedness and reduce the impact of EWEs.

1. Introduction

Extreme weather events (EWEs) have quintupled over the past 50 years.¹ Even small increases in global temperatures cause significant changes in the frequency and intensity of heatwaves and heavy rainfall.² An estimated 61% of terrestrial land experienced an increase in days with intense precipitation between the periods 1961–1990 and 2014–2023. Moreover, in 2019–2023, the risk of very high or extremely

high wildfires increased by 11% compared to 2003–2007.³

EWEs, with their well-documented impacts on health,^{3–7} are a key driver for international climate action and diplomacy. Following the 2024 Conference of the Parties (COP29), the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasised that health is "the argument for climate action", citing mounting evidence of climate-related health risks to push for more ambitious global efforts.⁸

EWEs also disrupt health services and systems, often overlooked in

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favour of individual health outcomes. The 2021 floods in Germany exemplify the destructive impact on critical health infrastructure, with approximately 180 primary care clinics either destroyed or rendered non-operational due to water and power outages, and nearly 70 hospitals affected.⁹ Recent floods in Spain also strained the health system by disrupting medicine supply chains, and causing power outages.¹⁰ Heatwaves significantly burden health systems too, increasing ambulance and Emergency Department (ED) utilisation, which can lead to system overload or necessitate adjustments in service delivery.^{11,12}

While some case studies document the impacts of EWEs on health systems, there is a lack of comprehensive mapping of these impacts across different healthcare delivery settings. This gap is largely due to the complexity of health systems, characterised by interdependent components, differences across health systems globally, and the challenge of disentangling health system impacts from health outcomes.

A 2017 narrative review¹³ laid the groundwork for analysing the effects of EWEs on health and social care systems in the United Kingdom (UK), offering a detailed overview of different impacts, including those concerning infrastructure functionality and medication quality. Given the frequency of EWEs and the growing scientific interest in this field, there is a need to consolidate evidence on the impacts of EWEs on health systems.

This systematic review of reviews aims to comprehensively map the impacts of EWEs on health services and systems across multiple healthcare delivery settings, including pre-hospital services, hospitals, primary care, elderly care, pharmacies, and public health departments. The review seeks to generate insights to anticipate emerging challenges, strengthen preparedness, and identify key indicators for assessing health system performance in response to floods and storms, heatwaves and cold spells, and wildfires. The primary outcome of interest is defined as “impacts on health services and systems”, encompassing effects observed across organisational domains such as infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, service utilisation, patient flow, surge capacity, and the availability of both material and human resources, as characterised within each delivery setting (operational definitions provided in Table 1).

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

Considering the scattered literature on the impacts of EWEs on health services and systems, a systematic review of reviews¹⁴ was considered the most suitable method to achieve the objective. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines¹⁵ were followed (Supplementary Material I: PRISMA Checklist). The review protocol was not pre-registered on a scientific platform.

2.2. Search strategy

A systematic literature search was carried out in PubMed, Scopus,

and Web of Science, employing a combination of two term clusters (Supplementary Material II: Term Clusters): one related to health systems and the other to EWEs. The search, performed in May 2024, was limited to reviews published from 2013 onwards; filters were applied to restrict the results to narrative reviews, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses. The literature search was restricted to publications from 2013 onwards to encompass the last decade of research, ensuring relevance to recent disaster occurrences, evolving conceptual frameworks, and contemporary approaches in public health and emergency management.

The study selection process followed these inclusion criteria: i) the study is a review (systematic, with or without meta-analysis, or narrative); ii) the study addresses the impacts of floods, storms, heatwaves, cold spells, or wildfires on health services and systems. Exclusion criteria included: i) studies focusing solely on health without addressing the health system; ii) studies published before the specified timeframe; iii) studies with unavailable full text. No language restrictions were applied.

The methodological quality of the records was critically appraised using the Joanna Briggs Institute Checklist for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses,¹⁶ with reviews classified as high-, medium-, or low-quality according to the number of “yes” responses across the 11 items reported in the checklist. Recognising that non-systematic narrative reviews were likely to fall within the low quality category, these were nonetheless retained, as they offered thematically relevant insights aligned with the aims of this review. The total number of records was divided into four subsets, each independently appraised in the main text by one of four reviewers using the selected tool. Prior to the appraisal, a calibration meeting was held among all reviewers to establish common criteria and ensure consistency in the evaluation process. Subsequently, one reviewer randomly checked 12 records (approximately 10% of the total) to verify the accuracy and validate the consistency of the classifications. A summary of methodological quality is presented in the Results section, with full details provided in the Supplementary Material V.

2.3. Data extraction and analysis

Selected records were entered into a Google Sheet database, and duplicates were removed. Four authors assessed the eligibility of articles for inclusion by first reviewing titles and abstracts, followed by full-text evaluations. Data extraction from the reviews was deductively carried out and the topics addressed by each review were thematically mapped to align with the study’s objectives. Information was extracted regarding the type of EWE, study characteristics, and the types of impacts on specific levels of care. Operational definitions were systematically relied upon to ensure consistency (Table 1).

2.4. Data synthesis and reporting

A data extraction table was developed to extract key information from the selected reviews, including review type, hazard type, affected care level, and impact type. A tabular representation of the most significant results is presented in Table 2.

Table 1

Operational definitions considered for data extraction and analysis.

Extreme weather event

A rare event for a specific location and time of year, typically as rare as or rarer than the 10th or 90th percentile of a probability distribution based on observations. The characteristics of EWEs can vary significantly by region¹⁷; those considered in this study are floods and storms, heatwaves and cold spells, and wildfires. These events were selected due to their wide spread, sudden-onset and highly destructive nature, as opposed to hazards such as droughts, which, although extreme, evolve more slowly and are less relevant from a perspective of health system impacts. Due to the heterogeneity in definitions and lack of clear indicators in some included studies, flexibility was applied in classifying certain conditions as EWEs. For instance, “days of extreme heat” with impacts similar to heatwaves were classified under heatwave impacts.

Health services and systems

Systems encompassing different healthcare delivery settings, including pre-hospital, hospital, primary care, elderly care, pharmacies, and the public health department. Within the hospital system, different care pathways were further distinguished: emergency, medical and surgical, and outpatient and Day Hospital pathways.¹⁸ When the specific level of care was unclear in the article, linguistic criteria were systematically applied for classification. For example, references to “mental health services” without further specification were included in the hospital system’s outpatient pathway, while “physician visits” were classified under primary care.

Impacts on health services and systems

Effects observed across various areas and functions of the health system, which include impacts on infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, healthcare service utilisation, patient flow, surge capacity, and resources, including both equipment and human resources.¹⁹

Table 2
Overview of the impacts of extreme weather events on the health system.

Extreme weather event	Area of impact	Pre-hospital	Hospital: emergency	Hospital: medical and surgical	Hospital: outpatient and Day Hospital	Primary and elderly care	Pharmacies	Public health department
Floods and storms	Infrastructure		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ED damaged and flooded ● Water and power outages, with failure of electric systems and equipment ● Loss of paper records, drug protocols, trials, and document 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Water and power outages, with failure of electric systems and equipment ● Loss of paper records, drug protocols, trials, and document 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dialysis units and mental health facilities damaged and flooded ● Water and power outages, with failure of electric systems and equipment ● Loss of paper records, drug protocols, trials, and document 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Primary care facilities damaged and flooded ● Failure of medical equipment and generators located in the basement ● Power outages in long-term care facilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pharmacy premises are damaged and flooded 	
	Access to care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rescuers inaccessibility to victims ● Challenging air rescue at night ● Rescue by boat difficult and expensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lower perceived ED care quality with delayed treatment ● Loss of phone line hinders dialling emergency number ● Road and lift failures limit access for the elderly ● Damages to buildings disrupt ED services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lower perceived care quality with delayed treatment ● Road and lift failures limit access for the elderly ● Damage of specialised units forces patients to travel long distances for care ● Damages to buildings disrupt medical and surgical services ● Elective surgeries are postponed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lower perceived care quality with delayed treatment ● Road and lift failures limit access for the elderly ● Shortage of rehab services and radiotherapy due to damages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disrupted transportation hinder access to primary care for those with limited mobility ● Disruption of home nursing for the elderly ● Impact on caregivers disrupt access to care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inability to contact prescribers and insurance challenges ● Damages to roads and closures 	
	Quality of care		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Power outages compromise the storage of refrigerated medications ● Disrupted access to potable water affects hygiene and sanitation ● Limited access to clinical records 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Power outages compromise the storage of refrigerated medications ● Disrupted access to potable water affects hygiene and sanitation ● Limited access to clinical records 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Power outages compromise the storage of refrigerated medications ● Disrupted access to potable water affects hygiene and sanitation ● Limited access to clinical records ● Shortening of duration of dialysis sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Understaffing and disaster-specific skill shortage ● Limited access to clinical records ● Hardship in maintaining medication regimes for evacuated elderly 		
	Service utilisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased callouts and dispatches of ambulances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of ED patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase in hospitalisations/hospital admissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of outpatient patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of primary care patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Contrasting evidence on the decrease/increase in prescriptions, dispensations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase in public health services provision (eg., water quality, surveillance)
	Surge capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Air transport of staff and stuff hindered by poor weather 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health needs surpass available first aid and injury care resources ● Shortage of equipment, medication and supplies due to obstacles affecting the supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Shortage and difficult transportation of electrical equipment ● Need for relocation of ICU patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Health needs surpass available radiotherapy and dialysis care resources ● Shortage of equipment, medication and supplies due to obstacles affecting the supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Insufficient emergency provisions ● Need for the distribution of essential goods (e. g., blankets) ● Increased needs for PTSD care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Need for task-shifting ● Shortage of medical supplies ● Need to switch to agile dispensation mechanisms (eg., drugs dispensed without prescriptions) 	
	Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rescuers suffer from PTSD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Difficulties in long-term staff retention after disasters ● Staff suffer from PTSD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Difficulties in long-term staff retention after disasters ● Disruption of respiratory equipment ● Staff suffer from PTSD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Difficulties in long-term staff retention after disasters ● Disruption of respiratory equipment ● Delivery problems of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Damage or loss of supportive tools (wheelchairs, hearing aids, etc.) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Impact on public health research due to damage to documents and specimens

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Table 2 (continued)

Extreme weather event	Area of impact	Pre-hospital	Hospital: emergency	Hospital: medical and surgical	Hospital: outpatient and Day Hospital	Primary and elderly care	Pharmacies	Public health department	
Heatwaves and cold spells	Infrastructure		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Damages to water supply system and medical equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Damages to water supply system and medical equipment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Staff suffer from PTSD ● Damages to water supply system and medical equipment 				
	Access to care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rescuers' access hampered by pavement failure, cracked rails, power losses ● <i>During cold spells:</i> longer ambulance response time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Delayed emergency care seeking during pregnancy ● Reaching hospitals is hard in remote, sparsely populated areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reaching hospitals is hard in remote, sparsely populated areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reaching hospitals is hard in remote, sparsely populated areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>During cold spells:</i> ice and snow disrupt homecare and community care services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>During cold spells:</i> ice and snow disrupt access to pharmacies 		
	Quality of care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deterioration of drugs in ambulances in extreme heat ● Fluctuation of vaporisers' output for field anesthesia ● <i>During cold spells:</i> deterioration of drugs in extreme cold 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Medications exceed recommended temperature threshold 					
	Service utilisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased callouts and dispatches of ambulances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of ED patients ● <i>During cold spells:</i> increased influx of ED patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase in hospitalisations/hospital admissions ● Longer lengths of hospital stay ● <i>During cold spells:</i> increase in hospital admissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of outpatients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of primary care patients ● <i>During cold spells:</i> increased influx of primary care patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased dispensation of psychotropic drugs 		
	Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Rescuer equipment suffers in extreme heat ● Increased risk of heat-related illnesses, physiological stress ● <i>During cold spells:</i> equipment suffers in extreme cold ● <i>During cold spells:</i> decrease in fine motor control, cognitive function 							
Wildfires	Infrastructure			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Closure of hospital wards because of fire and smoke 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Closure of hospital wards because of fire and smoke 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Primary care facilities damaged 			
	Access to care		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Barriers to accessing the hospital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Barriers to accessing the hospital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Barriers to accessing the hospital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Barriers to accessing primary care 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Disrupted access to prescription of opioids 		
	Service utilisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased callouts and dispatches of ambulances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of ED patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increase in hospitalisations/hospital admissions ● Increase in re-hospitalisation for the elderly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of outpatient patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased influx of primary care patients 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Increased dispensation of respiratory medications 		
	Surge capacity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Displaced populations from wildfires strain 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Exceeding of hospital's ICU capacity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Displaced populations from wildfires strain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Displaced populations from wildfires strain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Displaced populations from wildfires strain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Displaced populations from wildfires strain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Displaced populations from wildfires strain

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Table 2 (continued)

Extreme weather event	Area of impact	Pre-hospital	Hospital: emergency	Hospital: medical and surgical	Hospital: outpatient and Day Hospital	Primary and elderly care	Pharmacies	Public health department
		host community health systems			host community health systems	host community health systems	host community health systems	strain host community health systems
	Resources		● Challenges in accessing medications, supplies and equipment	● Challenges in accessing medications, supplies and equipment	● Challenges in accessing medications, supplies and equipment			

While all reviews were included regardless of their searching strategy to ensure a comprehensive mapping of evidence, the presentation of results emphasises quantitative findings from meta-analyses (when present), followed by those from systematic and narrative reviews.

3. Results

Of the 2108 records identified, 668 duplicates were removed, leaving 1440 for screening. After title and abstract screening, 1286 were excluded, followed by 40 more after full-text screening, leaving 114 records for inclusion (Fig. 1: PRISMA flowchart and Supplementary Material III: Records included). Of these, 19 performed a meta-analysis, 48 were systematic reviews and 47 were narrative non-systematic.

The EWEs most addressed by the included reviews were heatwaves and cold spells (74% of meta-analyses, 60% of systematic reviews and 68% of narrative reviews), whereas the most frequently considered healthcare delivery setting was the hospital (84% of meta-analyses, 81% of systematic reviews and 96% of narrative reviews) (Table 3).

3.1. Prehospital system

3.1.1. Floods and storms

Floods and storms impact the ability of rescuers to reach people in need, as disrupted roads impede ambulances to rescue victims.^{20–24} Alternative means of transport are helicopters and boats, but they need to be available and present limitations (i.e., the need to operate in daylight,²³ cost and time constraints²²). Ambulance callouts and dispatches increase, including for assisting those relying on ventilators and oxygen, disrupted by power outages.²¹ Transporting additional staff and supplies in the affected areas is challenging due to adverse weather.²³ The main impact on human resources concerns the potential onset of Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).²⁵ A study²⁶ included in the review from Massazza et al. (2022) highlighted that 11.8 % of the rescue personnel suffered from PTSD up to seven years after responding to a flood in Italy.

3.1.2. Heatwaves and cold spells

The main impact of extreme temperatures concerns a rise in ambulance callouts and dispatches during and after heatwaves, with reports of increases in the pooled relative risk (RR) of ambulance dispatch during heatwaves ranging from 2% to 7%, depending on the heatwave definition.^{27,28} These increases are due to exacerbations of cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, respiratory and renal diseases, neurological complaints, and suicide attempts.^{27,29–33} Heatwaves can hinder ambulance access due to pavement failure, cracking railway lines, and power losses, as seen in Australia,^{24,34} whereas cold spells may prolong response time.¹³ Extreme heat can degrade drugs, especially those transported on ambulances, and affect anesthesia vaporizers' output.^{35–37} Similarly, drug deterioration may occur during cold spells.^{35,37} Rescue equipment may be disrupted in extreme heat (eg., electronic screens shut down, polyvinyl chloride components become malleable) and cold (eg., batteries drain, crystals in screens freeze).^{35,38} Human resources face an

increased risk of heat-related illnesses and physiological stress, and a potential decrease in fine motor control and cognitive function during cold spells.^{35,38}

3.1.3. Wildfires

Wildfires increase ambulance callouts and dispatches for asthma, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD), and diabetes due to rising particulate matter (PM) levels.³⁹ Barros et al. (2023)³⁹ reported a 1% increase in the odds ratio (OR) of ambulance dispatches for asthma and COPD with a 10 µg/m³ increment in 1-h PM_{2.5} levels in Canada, with diabetic-related dispatches rising by 7.5–10.4% within 24h following exposure. Post-wildfire displacement further strains host communities' health systems.⁴⁰

3.2. Hospital system

3.2.1. Floods and storms

Floods and storms damage hospitals, endanger EDs, medical and surgical wards, and ambulatories.^{20,22,23,41–44} Power outages disrupt gas pipelines, utilities, temperature control, sewage, storage, life support systems, medical and communication technologies, air and water quality systems, sanitation processes, lifts and freezers.^{13,21–24,42,43,45,46} Loss of paper records¹³ impairs patient monitoring^{23,45} while power outages can affect radiology, blood banks and refrigerated medications.⁴⁵ Elective surgeries are often postponed,²² and Intensive Care Unit (ICU) or dialysis patients may be relocated to leave space for new patients.^{45,47}

Patients' perception of care quality diminishes, especially in case of power outages.^{20,21,42,43,45,46,48} Increased health needs strain staff, who may be difficult to retain post-disaster.^{42,45} Mass casualty events deplete analgesics, equipment, medications, and supplies due to damages and supply chains disruptions.^{42,49}

3.2.1.1. Utilisation of emergency care services. Floods and storms can increase ED visits,^{44,50} due to hypothermia,^{21,23,51} injuries,^{24,51,52} lower extremity cellulitis, dermatological and gastrointestinal conditions,⁵¹ diabetes complications, renal failure, hemodialysis, respiratory conditions,^{47,51,53–55} carbon monoxide and gasoline poisonings,²¹ oxygen/medication refills,⁴⁴ pregnancy-related mental health concerns and complications^{43,48,52} and, in case of power outages, failure of electricity-dependent medical devices.^{21,45,48} Paediatric ED visits may increase for poisoning,^{51,56} diarrheal illness and, in case of power outages, failure of electricity-dependent medical devices.^{48,56}

3.2.1.2. Utilisation of medical and surgical services. Floods and storms can increase hospitalisations,^{57,58} due to cardiovascular conditions such as heart attacks and strokes, respiratory ailments, including COPD, schizophrenia, and renal failure from missed dialysis.^{5,21,29,40,47,48,50,51,54,59} ICU admissions may rise due to heart failure,⁵⁰ and paediatric hospitalisations may also increase.⁶⁰

3.2.1.3. Utilisation of outpatient services and day hospital. Floods and storms can increase outpatient visits for injuries (e.g., lacerations,

Fig. 1. PRISMA flowchart detailing the screening process and selection of final records.

abrasions, wounds),⁵¹ infectious diseases, leptospirosis, skin or soft tissue infections, diarrhea, intestinal infections, impetigo, conjunctivitis, cellulitis, febrile illnesses, cardiovascular complaints and mental health consultations.^{51,61}

3.2.2. Heatwaves and cold spells

Heatwaves affect water supply systems, medical equipment functionality,^{13,38} and storage of temperature-sensitive drugs.⁶² Hospital access becomes difficult, especially for pregnancy visits⁶² and for remote communities.⁶³

3.2.2.1. Utilisation of emergency care services. Heatwaves significantly increase ED visits,^{13,33,34,58,63–72} particularly for elders and youths⁷³ and during transition months,⁶⁹ due to direct heat illness, dehydration, headache, hyper/hypotension, and disorders of fluid and electrolyte balance.^{73–76} A study in Georgia (US) reported an RR of 1.06 (0.99–1.14) for ED presentations due to heat illness and dehydration.⁷⁵ Other reasons include multiple sclerosis exacerbation,⁷⁶ cardiovascular conditions, respiratory and renal diseases,^{29,31,33,59,63,73,74,77,78} occupational injuries, diabetes,²⁹ emergency cesarean sections and preterm contractions related to fatigue and dehydration,^{37,62} and mental health disorders.^{32,79}

Cold spells result in ED visits increase for cardiovascular diseases and injuries from falls on ice and snow.¹³ Increases were also noted for paediatric ED visits during heatwaves for asthma and cold spells for respiratory diseases.⁸⁰

3.2.2.2. Utilisation of medical and surgical services. Both heatwaves and cold spells lead to increase in hospitalisations^{33,34,42,57,58,63,64,67,70,75,81–86}; for heatwaves, it is due to direct heat illness, dehydration, and fluid and

Table 3

Summary of the characteristics of the included reviews.

Type of review	Frequency (%)
Metanalysis	19 (16.7 %)
Systematic	48 (42.1 %)
Narrative	47 (41.2 %)
Hazard^a	
Floods and storms	44 (38.6 %)
Heatwaves and cold spells	75 (65.8 %)
Wildfires	42 (36.8 %)
Unspecified extreme weather event	4 (3.5 %)
Healthcare delivery setting	
Pre-hospital	33 (29.0 %)
Hospital	99 (86.8 %)
Primary and elderly care	31 (27.2 %)
Pharmacies	18 (15.8 %)
Public health department	11 (9.7 %)

^a A review can cover multiple hazards and multiple healthcare delivery settings, which is why some percentages exceed 100 %.

electrolyte disorders,^{42,75,84,87} cardiovascular diseases, respiratory and renal diseases,^{13,24,29–31,33,42,52,59,63,69,72,74,77,78,84,86–93} diabetes, Alzheimer’s disease, non-cholera diarrhea, and infectious diseases in the elderly.^{55,77,84,91,94,95} Pregnant women face higher risks of antepartum hemorrhage and hypertensive pregnancy complications during heatwaves.^{72,82} Mental health-related hospitalisations increase during heatwaves,^{70,90,95–98} with longer and more intense heatwaves increasing the risk of hospital admission to a greater extent than shorter heatwaves.³² Paediatric hospitalisations also rise during heatwaves, due to respiratory and renal diseases and cases of acute bronchiolitis in children under two

years.^{31,71,80}

During cold spells, hospitalisations typically rise due to dementia, cardiovascular diseases (myocardial infarction, heart disease, hypertension, cerebrovascular diseases, ischemic heart diseases, and stroke), fall-related injuries on days with snow and ice, and diabetes.^{55,76,84,87,89,90,98}

3.2.2.3. Utilisation of outpatient services and day hospital. Heatwaves primarily impact outpatient services with increased visits for kidney diseases and pneumonia.^{90,99}

3.2.3. Wildfires

Wildfires hinder hospital access,¹⁰⁰ and disrupt the availability of medications, supplies and equipment.⁴⁹ Fire and smoke may force wards closures, compromising patient safety,⁴¹ while ICU capacity can become strained.¹⁰⁰

3.2.3.1. Utilisation of emergency care services. ED visits increase during wildfires, due to elevated PM concentrations,^{56,58,66,101–104} with surges in cases of cardiovascular and respiratory conditions.^{36,39,66,86,93,100,103–110} A meta-analysis¹¹¹ found a 0.36% (0.19–0.53%) increase in respiratory-related ED visits per 1- $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ rise in PM_{2.5}. Pediatric ED visits also rise, particularly for asthma and other respiratory conditions.^{105,112,113}

3.2.3.2. Utilisation of medical and surgical services. Wildfires lead to increased hospitalisations due to elevated PM concentrations,^{56,103–105,114} for respiratory conditions,^{36,39,40,86,93,99–108,111} cardiovascular diseases,^{39,103,104,108,109} mood disorders³² and diabetes.⁵⁵ Elders with pre-existing cardiorespiratory conditions and COPD face higher rehospitalization risk.¹⁰⁴ ICU admissions for cardiovascular issues also rise and hospitalisations increase for respiratory conditions and dermatitis in children.^{100,112,114}

3.2.3.3. Utilisation of outpatient services and day hospital. Outpatient visits rise for conditions linked to smoke and PM exposure,^{102,104,105} including dermatological issues^{20,114} cardiovascular concerns and mental health issues.^{61,100} Pediatric patients under 15 are more frequently seen for respiratory problems, pruritus, and conjunctivitis.^{20,105,112,114}

3.3. Primary care system

3.3.1. Floods and storms

Floods and storms damage primary care clinics, including medical equipment and basement-located generators.^{21,23} Disruption of transportations and infrastructure interrupt home nursing^{22,45,66} and limit elderly access to primary care.⁶⁶ Power outages impact those reliant on electrically powered equipment at home or in nursing homes.²¹ Medical records loss hinders patient identification and medication requirements during evacuations, with reports of 48.4% of evacuees not bringing their medications to shelters, leading to treatment disruption and a secondary health needs surge.^{21,115} Primary care visits increase for up to 12 months after the event, mainly for vaccinations, routine care, prescription refills, cardiovascular diseases and chest pain.^{50,51,56,115,116} Supportive tools (e.g., wheelchairs, hearing aids, glasses) may be lost during evacuation.¹¹⁷

3.3.2. Heatwaves and cold spells

Heatwaves increase primary care services usage,^{63,72} with Moon et al. (2021)⁸⁵ reporting an RR of 1.38 (1.31–1.46) for general practitioners (GP) visits for diabetes. Conversely, a decrease in primary care visits for myocardial infarction was reported.⁸¹

During cold spells, increases in primary care visits are reported for respiratory conditions,¹³ though snow and ice can disrupt access to

primary care clinics, homecare and community care services.¹³

3.3.3. Wildfires

Wildfires disrupt primary care facilities access, posing a continuity of care challenge for patients with chronic conditions like diabetes.^{55,100} Visits rise significantly during wildfires, particularly for respiratory issues and asthma, with physician visits linked to elevated PM levels. Studies report increases in visits for pulmonary symptoms, otitis media, and cardiovascular conditions, especially among the elderly.^{39,56,86,93,101,104–106,109,114}

3.4. Pharmacies

3.4.1. Floods and storm

Floods and storms disrupt pharmacy infrastructure,^{56,118} damage equipment and supplies, and limit access to medications.^{44,56,117} After Hurricane Sandy, 74% of pharmacies experienced structural damage, with 71% reopening within a month, though many had to replace medications or equipment.⁵⁶ Some reviews report declines in e-prescribing and medication dispensation post-storms,^{48,56} while dispensation of antidiarrheal, electrolytes, pulmonary relievers, and oral corticosteroids increases.^{48,93,115} Pharmacists may assume non-traditional roles, such as conducting health assessments in shelters, triaging patients, and providing toxicology consultations.¹¹⁸

3.4.2. Heatwaves and cold spells

Heatwaves increase the dispensation of psychotropic medications, including antidepressants, antipsychotics, anxiolytics, tricyclics, mood stabilisers, addiction treatment drugs, and diuretics.⁷²

During snowstorms, pharmacy access is hindered, with US pharmacists relying on snowmobile teams for medication deliveries.¹¹⁸

3.4.3. Wildfires

Medication use for obstructive airway diseases rises after wildfires.¹⁰⁴ A study in Spain¹¹⁹ included in Youssouf et al. (2014) found a 10.3% increase in consumption among male pensioners and a 12.9% increase among female pensioners in affected areas compared to unaffected ones. Dispensation of respiratory medications, including pulmonary relievers, oral steroids, asthma treatments, and anxiolytics also increases.

3.5. Public health department

3.5.1. Floods and storms

Power outages impact food refrigeration, water supply systems, and disinfection, increasing monitoring requirements.⁴⁸ Concerns have been raised about potential water contamination from radioactive materials released due to flooding of nuclear medicine facilities.⁴⁴ Public health departments face higher workloads due to increased surveillance of infections or food poisoning.^{48,120,121}

3.5.2. Quality of included records

The quality of the included reviews was assessed using the Joanna Briggs Institute Checklist for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses,¹⁶ with the number of positive responses used as an indicator of quality. Reviews were classified as high-quality, medium-quality, or low-quality. As expected, given the inclusion of both non-systematic narrative reviews and systematic reviews (with or without meta-analysis), methodological quality varied considerably. Overall, 21.1% of the reviews were rated as high-quality, 41.2% as medium-quality, and 37.7% as low-quality. Specifically, 78.8% of narrative reviews were judged to be of low-quality compared to 12.5% of systematic reviews and 0% of meta-analyses. Thematically, 45.5% of the reviews addressing floods and storms were of low quality, as well as 31.8% of those focusing on heatwaves and cold spells, and 42.1% of those focusing on wildfires.

4. Discussion

This overview of reviews systematically mapped and analysed the impacts of floods and storms, heatwaves and cold spells, and wildfires on health services and systems. The findings establish a foundation for exploring how EWEs affecting the health system can affect health, provide a basis for developing tools for rapid healthcare needs assessments (Supplementary Material IV), or to enhance preparedness (e.g., design simulation scenarios or guide plans), and can support the identification of indicators to assess health system's performance during disasters. Overall, the findings highlight research density across areas, and the heterogeneity of evidence and impacts across different healthcare delivery settings and hazard types, offering a comprehensive mapping with practical implications for decision-makers.

Floods and storms disrupt hospital and pre-hospital systems through infrastructure damage and road closures. Hospital administrators should take preparedness and response actions to address water-related damage to equipment, power generators, control systems, and clinical documentation, which can trigger cascading effects potentially requiring time-sensitive hospital evacuations amid power outages.¹²² Meanwhile, local disaster managers should plan for and mitigate the impact of road closures, which delay rescue and complicate time-sensitive emergency care delivery. Several original studies explored the impact of flooding on ambulance access in different regions¹²³⁻¹²⁹, showing that individuals in areas inaccessible to ambulances may benefit from preemptive evacuations.

Heatwaves strain health systems primarily by increasing ambulance dispatch, ED visits, hospitalisations, and primary care consultations, due to direct heat exposure and the exacerbation of chronic conditions. Paganini et al. (2023)¹³⁰ describe three phases contributing to ED overload during heatwaves: *input*, with increased patient flow; *throughput*, where resource limitations and delays occur; and *output*, with delayed discharges and transfers. Hospital administrators should prepare for and implement surge capacity and ensure the redistribution of resources to maintain service continuity during these peaks. To alleviate ED congestion, the study suggests implementing effective heat warning systems, providing targeted education to vulnerable populations, and reinforcing primary care—actions that require coordinated efforts by public health officials, primary care network coordinators, and GPs. Thus, responding to heatwaves requires strategies beyond mass casualty approaches, focusing on sustaining response efforts during prolonged emergencies.^{131,132}

Evidence on the health system impacts of wildfires remains limited to the increased healthcare utilisation linked to PM concentrations. However, wildfires also damage infrastructure and disrupt access to care, exacerbating service demands. To address this, community-based policies could help reduce healthcare overload while accounting for the vulnerability of stretched systems. Joint efforts by local health and disaster managers, in collaboration with community-based organisations and volunteer groups, can foster community leadership for mutual aid, educating residents on evacuation plans, ensuring patients update medication lists, and deploying digital mental health support.^{133,134}

It is highly desirable for health systems to translate these findings into actionable recommendations that promote coordinated efforts among representatives across all delivery settings, in collaboration with local and regional disaster management systems and the communities they serve. For instance, in anticipation of flooding, health systems could optimise response by using flood risk maps to identify accessible ambulance routes, plan for increased demand by scaling up resources, secure critical hospital infrastructure to prevent damage, ensure patient continuity of care through evacuation strategies for homebound individuals, and enhance individual resilience by providing self-management guidelines on medication stockpiling.

This review identifies gaps for future research. While flood impacts on infrastructure, patient flow, and resources are well-documented, the effects of heat on human resources, equipment, and medicines remain

unclear. Evidence on cold waves is scarce, and wildfire studies focus mainly on healthcare utilisation after PM exposure, overlooking broader system disruptions. Hospital impacts are often vague, rarely distinguishing between wards. Future research should examine effects on critical services such as dialysis, paediatrics, and intensive care.

There remains room for improvement in the overall quality of the reviews, especially those focusing on floods and wildfires. Consulting the JBI Checklist for Systematic Reviews and Research Syntheses¹⁶ throughout the review process may help scholars ensure adherence to key methodological standards. In this regard, it is worth acknowledging that several items in the appraisal checklist are specifically formulated to comply with methodological standards applicable to systematic reviews and meta-analyses. As a result, narrative reviews inherently fall short of meeting many of the criteria stipulated in the JBI instrument.¹⁶ More remarkable, however, are the findings revealing that even certain systematic reviews exhibited only moderate methodological quality.

Methodological and content-related limitations of this study can be distinguished. The former encompass the loss of granularity in the data from the inclusion of reviews rather than original studies, which may overlook outlier cases. For instance, while most floods are associated with increased ED visits, evidence from floods in Emilia-Romagna, Italy,¹³⁵ showed a greater demand for primary care and social services instead. The lack of distinction between studies conducted in high-, middle-, and low-income countries may have led to overgeneralized conclusions, potentially overlooking critical context-specific evidence on the impacts of floods in low and middle income countries, where limited resources often result in more severe and distinct outcomes. Furthermore, selected operational definitions and theoretical frameworks, although useful for cross-study comparisons, may have constrained the scope of analysis and limited the identification of alternative perspectives.

Content-related limitations include the disproportionate focus on certain hazards, likely resulting in underreporting of impacts for less-studied events. Health system impacts that are immediate and directly linked to EWEs tend to be more documented, whereas long-term or indirect effects are more difficult to capture and thus often overlooked. Moreover, insufficient detail in many reviews regarding specific healthcare delivery settings, such as primary care, may contribute to the underestimation of impacts in those domains.

The strengths of this work lie in systematically mapping recent evidence, categorising impacts across care levels, and distinguishing between hazards to obtain an easy-to-consult overview for other scholars and policy-makers. The findings provide a clear framework for disaster preparedness and offer insights for future research and resilience-building initiatives.

5. Conclusions

This review identified and systematised the impacts of EWEs on health services and systems, providing key insights for disaster preparedness. Understanding how different hazards affect specific health system components enables targeted actions to mitigate future impacts and strengthen overall health system resilience.

Author statements

Ethical approval

Ethical approval was not required for this study as it is a review of previously published literature.

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Competing interests

No competing interests to declare.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2025.106049>.

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